

SPSS syntaxes

SPSS Syntaxes

Raw data exploration

```
GLM M1 M2 M3 M4 M5
/WSFACTOR=Blocks 5 Difference
/METHOD=SSTYPE(3)
/EMMEANS=TABLES(OVERALL)
/EMMEANS=TABLES(Blocks) COMPARE ADJ(LSD)
/PRINT=DESCRIPTIVE ETASQ OPOWER
/CRITERIA=ALPHA(.05)
/WSDESIGN=Blocks.
```

Signal Detection Theory

Calculation of d' and c indexes

```
COMPUTE target = Hit+Miss.
COMPUTE lure = FA + CR.
COMPUTE usn=probit(Miss/target).
COMPUTE un=probit(CR/lure).
COMPUTE d'=UN-USN.
COMPUTE c=(UN+USN)/2.
EXECUTE .
```

Basic Statistical Descriptions of the Four SDT Responses

```
EXAMINE VARIABLES=Hit Miss CR FA
/ID=ID
/PLOT BOXPLOT STEMLEAF HISTOGRAM NPLOT
/COMPARE GROUPS
/PERCENTILES(5,10,25,50,75,90,95) HAVERAGE
/STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES EXTREME
/CINTERVAL 95
/MISSING LISTWISE
/NOTOTAL.
```

Basic Statistical Descriptions of the Eight Response Characteristic

```
DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet1.
EXAMINE VARIABLES=Zcorrect_response_mean ZCV Zd' Zc ZSs ZSp ZTI ZTII
/PLOT BOXPLOT STEMLEAF NPLOT
/COMPARE GROUPS
/STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES
/CINTERVAL 95
/MISSING LISTWISE
/NOTOTAL.
```

Cluster Analysis, Centroid Model

K-Means Clustering Analysis of Eight Response Characteristics (Clustering A)

Agglomerative hierarchical clustering

```
DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet2.
CLUSTER ZMean_CR ZCV_CR Zd' Zc ZSs ZSp ZTI ZTII
/METHOD WARD
/MEASURE=SEUCLID
/PRINT SCHEDULE
/PRINT DISTANCE
/PLOT DENDROGRAM VICICLE.
```

3K-means clustering

```
QUICK CLUSTER ZGM ZCV Zd' Zc ZSs ZTI ZSp ZTII
/MISSING=LISTWISE
/CRITERIA=CLUSTER(3) MXITER(10) CONVERGE(0)
/METHOD=KMEANS(NOUPDATE)
```

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```
/SAVE CLUSTER DISTANCE  
/PRINT ID(Subject) INITIAL ANOVA CLUSTER DISTAN.
```

Principal Component Analysis

```
FACTOR  
/VARIABLES Mean CV d' c Ss Sp TI TII  
/MISSING LISTWISE  
/ANALYSIS Mean CV d' c Ss Sp TI TII  
/PRINT UNIVARIATE INITIAL CORRELATION SIG KMO EXTRACTION ROTATION FSCORE  
/FORMAT SORT  
/PLOT EIGEN ROTATION  
/CRITERIA FACTORS(2) ITERATE(25)  
/EXTRACTION PC  
/CRITERIA ITERATE(25)  
/ROTATION VARIMAX  
/SAVE REG(ALL)  
/METHOD=CORRELATION.
```

K-Means Clustering of FS (Clustering B)

Agglomerative hierarchical clustering

```
DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet5.  
CLUSTER FAC1_1 FAC2_1  
/METHOD WARD  
/MEASURE=SEUCLID  
/PRINT SCHEDULE  
/PRINT DISTANCE  
/PLOT DENDROGRAM VICICLE.
```

3K-means clustering

```
QUICK CLUSTER FAC1_1 FAC2_1  
/MISSING=LISTWISE  
/CRITERIA=CLUSTER(3) MXITER(10) CONVERGE(0)  
/METHOD=KMEANS(NOUPDATE)  
/SAVE CLUSTER DISTANCE  
/PRINT ID(Subject) INITIAL ANOVA CLUSTER DISTAN.
```

ROC Space

K-Means Clustering of Two-Dimensional ROC Space (Clustering C)

Agglomerative hierarchical clustering

```
DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet6.  
CLUSTER ZSs ZTI  
/METHOD WARD  
/MEASURE=SEUCLID  
/PRINT SCHEDULE  
/PRINT DISTANCE  
/PLOT DENDROGRAM VICICLE.
```

3K-means clustering

```
QUICK CLUSTER ZSs ZTI  
/MISSING=LISTWISE  
/CRITERIA=CLUSTER(3) MXITER(10) CONVERGE(0)  
/METHOD=KMEANS(NOUPDATE)  
/SAVE CLUSTER DISTANCE  
/PRINT ID(ID) INITIAL ANOVA CLUSTER DISTAN.
```

Cross table clustering A X clustering B

```
DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet12.  
CROSSTABS  
/TABLES=Clustering_A BY Clustering_B
```

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```
/FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES  
/STATISTICS=CHISQ CC CORR  
/CELLS=COUNT  
/COUNT ROUND CELL.
```

Clustering Comparison

Cross table clustering A X clustering C

```
CROSSTABS  
/TABLES=Clustering_A BY Clustering_C  
/FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES  
/STATISTICS=CHISQ CC CORR  
/CELLS=COUNT  
/COUNT ROUND CELL.
```

Cross table clustering B X clustering C

```
CROSSTABS  
/TABLES=Clustering_B BY Clustering_C  
/FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES  
/STATISTICS=CHISQ CC CORR  
/CELLS=COUNT  
/COUNT ROUND CELL.
```

Tables

Clustering (A,B)	1	2	3	N
1	2	11	0	13
2	2	0	11	13
3	23	0	0	23
N	27	11	11	

Clustering (A,C)	1	2	3	N
1	12	0	1	13
2	0	4	9	13
3	0	0	23	23
N	12	4	33	

Clustering (A,C)	1	2	3	N
1	1	0	26	27
2	11	0	0	11
3	0	4	7	11
N	12	4	33	

R code

Three typical indices used for comparison between partitions

Comparing partitions (CB, 2022), R syntax

```
# reads the attributed groups resulting from three SPSS analyses A, B and C  
data=read.csv2("ClustersSubjectsSPSS.csv")
```

```
# load the R package "partitionComparison"  
library(partitionComparison)
```

```
# transforms the memberships into objects of class "Partition"
```

```
A = new("Partition", data$Clustering_A)
```

```
B = new("Partition", data$Clustering_B)
```

```
C = new("Partition", data$Clustering_C)
```

```
# creates cross-classification contingency tables
```

```
table(A,B)
```

```
table(A,C)
```

```
table(B,C)
```

```
# computes the Rand index, the Jaccard coefficient and Meila's index "Variation of Information"
```

```
randIndex(A,B)
```

```
jaccardCoefficient(A,B)
```

```
variationOfInformation(A,B)
```

```
randIndex(A,C)
```

```
jaccardCoefficient(A,C)
```

```
variationOfInformation(A,C)
```

```
randIndex(B,C)
```

```
jaccardCoefficient(B,C)
```

```
variationOfInformation(B,C)
```